

2.D.3 Statement by Reference/Optimized Implementations' Owner(s)

The following must also be included:

I, Martin Avendaño of Facultad de Matemáticas, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Madrid 28040 SPAIN , am the owner of the submitted reference implementation and optimized implementations and hereby grant the U.S. Government and any interested party the right to reproduce, prepare derivative works based upon, distribute copies of, and display such implementations for the purposes of the post-quantum algorithm public review and evaluation process, and implementation if the corresponding cryptosystem is selected for standardization and as a standard, notwithstanding that the implementations may be copyrighted or copyrightable.

Signed: Martin Avendaño
Title: Profesor Titular de Álgebra
Date: 31/05/2023
Place: Madrid, Spain

2.D.1 Statement by Each Submitter

I, Martin Avendaño of , Facultad de Matemáticas, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Madrid 28040 SPAIN, do hereby declare that the cryptosystem, reference implementation, or optimized implementations that I have submitted, known as DME-SIGN, is my own original work, or if submitted jointly with others, is the original work of the joint submitters.

I further declare that (check one):

- I do not hold and do not intend to hold any patent or patent application with a claim or that could be amended to include a claim that may cover the cryptosystem, reference implementation, or optimized implementations that I have submitted, known as DME-SIGN; **OR** (check one or both of the following):

I do hereby acknowledge and agree that my submitted cryptosystem will be provided to the public for review and will be evaluated by NIST, and that it might not be selected for standardization by NIST. I further acknowledge that I will not receive financial or other compensation from the U.S. Government for my submission. I certify that, to the best of my knowledge, I have fully disclosed all patents and patent applications which may cover my cryptosystem, reference implementation or optimized implementations. I also acknowledge and agree that the U.S. Government may, during the public review and the evaluation process, and, if my submitted cryptosystem is selected for standardization, during the lifetime of the standard, modify my submitted cryptosystem's specifications (e.g., to protect against a newly discovered vulnerability).

I acknowledge that NIST will announce any selected cryptosystem(s) and proceed to publish the draft standards for public comment

I do hereby agree to provide the statements required by Sections 2.D.2 and 2.D.3, below, for any patent or patent application identified to cover the practice of my cryptosystem, reference implementation or optimized implementations and the right to use such implementations for the purposes of the public review and evaluation process.

I acknowledge that, during the post-quantum algorithm evaluation process, NIST may remove my cryptosystem from consideration for standardization. If my cryptosystem (or the derived cryptosystem) is removed from consideration for standardization or withdrawn from consideration by all submitter(s) and owner(s), I understand that rights granted and assurances made under Sections 2.D.1, 2.D.2 and 2.D.3, including use rights of the reference and optimized implementations, may be withdrawn by the submitter(s) and owner(s), as appropriate.

Signed: Martin Avendaño
Title: Profesor Titular de Álgebra
Date: 05/31/2023
Place: Madrid, Spain

2.D.2 Statement by Patent (and Patent Application) Owner(s)

If there are any patents (or patent applications) identified by the submitter, including those held by the submitter, the following statement must be signed by each and every owner, or each owner's authorized representative, of each patent and patent application identified.

I, Ignacio Luengo , of Facultad de Matemáticas, Universidad Complutense de Madrid. Plaza de Ciencias 3, 28040 Madrid, Spain , am the owner or authorized representative of the owner (print full name, if different than the signer) of the following patent(s) and/or patent application(s): None , and do hereby commit and agree to grant to any interested party on a worldwide basis, if the cryptosystem known as DME-SIGN is selected for standardization, in consideration of its evaluation and selection by NIST, a non-exclusive license for the purpose of implementing the standard (check one):

- *without compensation and under reasonable terms and conditions that are demonstrably free of any unfair discrimination, **OR***
- *under reasonable terms and conditions that are demonstrably free of any unfair discrimination.*

I further do hereby commit and agree to license such party on the same basis with respect to any other patent application or patent hereafter granted to me, or owned or controlled by me, that is or may be necessary for the purpose of implementing the standard.

I further do hereby commit and agree that I will include, in any documents transferring ownership of each patent and patent application, provisions to ensure that the commitments and assurances made by me are binding on the transferee and any future transferee.

I further do hereby commit and agree that these commitments and assurances are intended by me to be binding on successors-in-interest of each patent and patent application, regardless of whether such provisions are included in the relevant transfer documents.

I further do hereby grant to the U.S. Government, during the public review and the evaluation process, and during the lifetime of the standard, a nonexclusive, nontransferable, irrevocable, paid-up worldwide license solely for the purpose of modifying my submitted cryptosystem's specifications (e.g., to protect against a newly discovered vulnerability) for incorporation into the standard.

*Signed: Ignacio Luengo
Title: Catedrático de Álgebra
Date: 31/05/2023
Place: Madrid, Spain*

2.D.2 Statement by Patent (and Patent Application) Owner(s)

If there are any patents (or patent applications) identified by the submitter, including those held by the submitter, the following statement must be signed by each and every owner, or each owner's authorized representative, of each patent and patent application identified.

I, Markel Epelde García, of BCAM, Edificio Sede. Barrio Sarriena, s/n, 48940 Leioa, Bizkaia, am the owner or authorized representative of the owner of the following patent(s) and/or patent application(s): (none), and do hereby commit and agree to grant to any interested party on a worldwide basis, if the cryptosystem known as DME-Sign is selected for standardization, in consideration of its evaluation and selection by NIST, a non-exclusive license for the purpose of implementing the standard (check one):

- without compensation and under reasonable terms and conditions that are demonstrably free of any unfair discrimination, **OR***
- under reasonable terms and conditions that are demonstrably free of any unfair discrimination.*

I further do hereby commit and agree to license such party on the same basis with respect to any other patent application or patent hereafter granted to me, or owned or controlled by me, that is or may be necessary for the purpose of implementing the standard.

I further do hereby commit and agree that I will include, in any documents transferring ownership of each patent and patent application, provisions to ensure that the commitments and assurances made by me are binding on the transferee and any future transferee.

I further do hereby commit and agree that these commitments and assurances are intended by me to be binding on successors-in-interest of each patent and patent application, regardless of whether such provisions are included in the relevant transfer documents.

I further do hereby grant to the U.S. Government, during the public review and the evaluation process, and during the lifetime of the standard, a nonexclusive, nontransferrable, irrevocable, paid-up worldwide license solely for the purpose of modifying my submitted cryptosystem's specifications (e.g., to protect against a newly discovered vulnerability) for incorporation into the standard.

*Signed: Markel Epelde García
Title: Postdoctoral Researcher
Date: May 31st, 2023
Place: Bilbao*

2.D.2 Statement by Patent (and Patent Application) Owner(s)

If there are any patents (or patent applications) identified by the submitter, including those held by the submitter, the following statement must be signed by each and every owner, or each owner's authorized representative, of each patent and patent application identified.

I, Pilar Coscojuela Escanilla, of 17 Antonio Toledano St, 4^oI, am the owner or authorized representative of the owner Ignacio Luengo Velasco of the following patent(s) and/or patent application(s): none, and do hereby commit and agree to grant to any interested party on a worldwide basis, if the cryptosystem known as DME-SIGN is selected for standardization, in consideration of its evaluation and selection by NIST, a non-exclusive license for the purpose of implementing the standard (check one):

- *without compensation and under reasonable terms and conditions that are demonstrably free of any unfair discrimination, **OR***
- *under reasonable terms and conditions that are demonstrably free of any unfair discrimination.*

I further do hereby commit and agree to license such party on the same basis with respect to any other patent application or patent hereafter granted to me, or owned or controlled by me, that is or may be necessary for the purpose of implementing the standard.

I further do hereby commit and agree that I will include, in any documents transferring ownership of each patent and patent application, provisions to ensure that the commitments and assurances made by me are binding on the transferee and any future transferee.

I further do hereby commit and agree that these commitments and assurances are intended by me to be binding on successors-in-interest of each patent and patent application, regardless of whether such provisions are included in the relevant transfer documents.

I further do hereby grant to the U.S. Government, during the public review and the evaluation process, and during the lifetime of the standard, a nonexclusive, nontransferrable, irrevocable, paid-up worldwide license solely for the purpose of modifying my submitted cryptosystem's specifications (e.g., to protect against a newly discovered vulnerability) for incorporation into the standard.

Signed: Pilar Coscojuela Escanilla

Title:

Date: May 31st, 2023

Place: Madrid